

VillageMath Educational Review

An International/Multidisciplinary Journal of
Network for Grassroots Science and Mathematics
Education (The VillageMath Network)

A publication of VillageMath Educational Services
(CAC RC: 4097888)

Volume 7, Issue 1

September, 2025

CODEN: VERIAU

Enhancing the Interest of Senior Secondary Students in Herbal Drug Discovery Using Guided Inquiry Instructional Strategy

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17205516>

Article History: Received 26th July, 2025; Revised 15th September, 2025; Published 27th September, 2025.

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How to Cite this Article:

Isah, I. (2025). Enhancing the Interest of Senior Secondary Students in Herbal Drug Discovery Using Guided Inquiry Instructional Strategy. *VillageMath Educational Review (VER)*, 7(1), 148-157. <https://ngsme.villagemath.net/journals/ver/v7i1/isah>

Abstract

This study investigated the effectiveness of the Guided Inquiry Instructional Strategy (GIIS) in enhancing the interest of Senior Secondary Students in herbal drug discovery in the Kabba-Bunu Education Zone of Kogi State, Nigeria. The increasing global reliance on herbal medicine, particularly in African societies, emphasize the need to integrate indigenous knowledge systems into formal science education. However, a major challenge facing science educators is the declining interest of students in pharmacognosy-related topics due to traditional, teacher-centered instructional methods. This quasi-experimental research employed a pre-test post-test non-equivalent control group design. Two groups of SS2 students were purposively selected from two comparable schools in the Kabba-Bunu education zone. The experimental group was taught using the GIIS approach, which actively involved students in identifying, classifying, and analyzing local medicinal plants through guided questioning, hands-on activities, and collaborative learning, while the control group

received conventional teaching method. An Interest Inventory Questionnaire on Herbal Drug Discovery (IIQ-HDD) was developed and validated to measure students' interest before and after the intervention. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions and ANCOVA for testing the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed a statistically significant improvement in the interest level of students exposed to GIIS compared to those taught with conventional method ($p < 0.05$). The study concluded that GIIS is an effective pedagogical approach for promoting interest in herbal drug discovery among secondary school students. It recommends the adoption of guided inquiry strategy in science classrooms and the incorporation of indigenous medicinal knowledge into the Nigerian secondary school curriculum to foster relevance, innovation, and engagement in science education.

Keywords: Guided Inquiry Instructional Strategy (GIIS), Herbal Drug Discovery, Science Education, Senior Secondary Students, Interest, African Indigenous Knowledge Systems

Introduction

Interest in integrating traditional herbal medicine into formal science education has risen significantly in Nigeria, fueled by growing global awareness of the value of indigenous remedies. According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2021), approximately 60% of African populations, including those in Ghana, Mali, and Nigeria, rely on herbal treatments for common ailments such as fever and malaria. Despite this widespread use, herbal medicine remains underrepresented in Nigerian school curricula, where pharmacognosy and ethnobotany are often taught through conventional, teacher-centered methods that fail to connect with students' cultural experiences.

Guided Inquiry Instructional Strategy (GIIS), a learner-centered approach rooted in constructivist theory, emphasizes students' active role in finding answers through structured exploration, inquiry, and reflection. In Nigeria, GIIS has shown considerable promise in improving both academic performance and interest, especially in science subjects. Olawuwo *et al.* (2024) report that Junior Secondary School (JSS) students taught Basic Science via Guided Inquiry achieved significantly higher than those taught through lecture methods in North Central (FCT, Niger & Nassarawa) Nigeria. Similarly, Tella and Ogundiya (2022) and Mgbomo *et al.* (2024) found that senior secondary students taught using guided discovery in chemistry and physics in Oyo and Rivers State respectively outperformed peers taught with conventional methods.

However, these studies have primarily focused on mainstream science topics rather than the culturally relevant domain of herbal drug discovery. This presents a critical gap, especially in areas like Kabba-Bunu Education Zone, Kogi State, where traditional medicine remains part of daily life and community health practices. Despite the potential for integrating local herbal knowledge into science teaching, there is little empirical evidence evaluating the efficacy of GIIS in this context.

In Nigeria, institutions like the National Institute for Pharmaceutical Research and Development (NIPRD) have made notable progress in developing herbal drugs, such as Niprisan to treat sickle cell disorders (Obodozie *et al.*, 2010), yet the link between classroom

science education and the phytomedicine R&D pipeline remains weak. Meanwhile, Nigerian pharmaceutical companies like Paxherbals combine ethnobotanical insights with laboratory research, highlighting the synergy of traditional knowledge and science. This underscores the need to introduce secondary school students early to the science underpinning herbal drug discovery, strengthening both scientific literacy and career pathways.

The herbal medicine discovery was underrepresented in secondary school Chemistry Education curriculum in Nigeria where pharmacognosy and ethnobotany are thought using the conventional methods. Those methods failed to connect the cultural experiences of students and had discouraged them from having interest in herbal drug discovery. In order to seek an instructional strategy that can enhance students' interest in herbal drugs discovery, Guided Inquiry strategy may be a solution to the problem. The problem of the study is therefore, to find out the effect of Guided Inquiry Instructional Strategy (GIIS) on senior secondary (SS) students' interest in herbal drugs discovery in Kabba Bunu Education Zone (KBEZ), Kogi State, Nigeria.

The adoption of Guided Inquiry Instructional Strategy (GIIS) in Chemistry classroom will encourage students and Chemist teachers to appreciate the use of the strategy in discovering herbal drugs. The findings of this research are hoped to assist Chemistry curriculum developers to include the use of GIIS in the planning and ensure the teachers abide by it. It is believed the research findings would help Kogi State Ministry of Education, secondary schools, Education Board and other educational stakeholders in the use of instructional strategy for teaching Chemistry for effective learning.

Building on these observations, this study aims to investigate the effect of Guided Inquiry Instructional Strategy (GIIS) on Senior Secondary School students' interest in herbal drug discovery in Kabba-Bunu, Kogi State, Nigeria. Specifically, it seeks to determine whether GDIS can effectively bridge the gap between students lived experiences with herbal medicine and academic science, thereby increasing engagement and fostering positive attitudes toward pharmacognosy and ethnopharmacology.

Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine the effect of Guided Inquiry Instructional Strategy on SS Students' Interest in Herbal Drugs Discovery in KBEZ, Kogi State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study determined the:

- i. effect of GIIS on SS Students Interest in Herbal Discovery in KBEZ, Kogi State, Nigeria.
- ii. effect of Gender on SS Students' Interest in Herbal Drugs Discovery in KBEZ, Kogi State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were asked to guide the study:

- i. What are the mean interest ratings of Senior Secondary students taught Herbal Drug Discovery using Guided Inquiry Instructional Strategy and those taught with Conventional Method?

- ii. What are the mean interest ratings of male and female Senior Secondary students taught Herbal Drug Discovery using Guided Inquiry Instructional Strategy?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance to guide the study:

- i. There is no significant difference between the Mean Interest Ratings of SS Students taught Herbal Drugs Discovery with GIIS and those taught with conventional method.
- ii. There is no significant difference between the Mean Interest Ratings of Male and Female SS Students taught Herbal Drugs Discovery using GIIS.

Methodology

The study adopted quasi-experimental design. Specifically, the pretest post-test non-equivalent group design was used. The population of the study was all SS2 science students in Senior Secondary Schools in Kogi State, Nigeria. Through balloting 50 SS2 students in Government Science Secondary School, Okedayo, were exposed to Guided Inquiry Instructional Strategy (GIIS) (Experimental Group) while 40 students in Comprehensive Secondary School, Kabba, were assigned to the conventional methods (Control Group). The instrument for data collection was 30-item Interest Inventory on Herbal Drugs Discovery (IID-HDD) and was validated by three experts in Chemistry Department in Kogi State College of Education (Technical), Mopa. The reliability of the instrument was ascertained by Cronbach Alpha's formula which yielded a coefficient 0.85. The data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions while the hypotheses were tested using ANCOVA at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

The results of this study are presented according to the research questions and hypotheses.

Research Question One

What are the mean interest ratings of Senior Secondary students taught Herbal Drug Discovery using Guided Inquiry Instructional Strategy and those taught with Conventional Method?

Table 1: Mean Interest Ratings of Senior Secondary students taught Herbal Drug Discovery using Guided Inquiry Instructional Strategy and those taught with Conventional Method

<i>Group</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Pre-Test</i>		<i>Post-Test</i>	
		<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>
<i>Experimental</i>	50	2.04	1.34	3.50	1.30
<i>Control</i>	40	2.01	1.23	2.10	1.33
<i>Mean Diff</i>		0.03		1.40	

The result as presented in Table 1 shows that in Pre-IID-HDD, the experimental group had a mean interest rating of 2.04 with a standard deviation of 1.34, while the control group had a mean interest rating 2.01 with a standard deviation of 1.23. Also, the result shows that the mean interest ratings of the experimental group in Post-IID-HDD is 3.50 with a standard deviation of 1.30 while the mean interest ratings in the control group is 2.10 with a standard deviation of 1.33. The mean difference in the Pre-IID-HDD between the experimental and the control group is 0.03 while in Post-IID-HDD, it is 1.40. This indicate that Guided Inquiry Instructional Strategy enhanced students' interest in Herbal Drugs Discovery.

Research Question Two

What are the mean interest ratings of male and female Senior Secondary students taught Herbal Drug Discovery using Guided Inquiry Instructional Strategy?

Table 2: Mean Interest Ratings of male and female Senior Secondary students taught Herbal Drug Discovery using Guided Inquiry Instructional Strategy

<i>Group</i>	<i>Pre-Test</i>		<i>Post-Test</i>		
	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>
<i>Male</i>	30	2.45	1.26	3.55	1.17
<i>Female</i>	20	2.43	1.04	3.55	1.25
<i>Mean Diff</i>		0.02		0.00	

Table 2 shows that in Pre-IID-HDD, the mean interest rating of male students in experimental group was 2.45 with standard deviation of 1.26 while the mean interest rating of the female students was 2.43 with the standard deviation of 1.04. In the Post-IID-HDD, the mean interest rating of the male students was 3.55 with the standard deviation of 1.17 while the female students mean interest rating was 3.55 with standard deviation of 1.25. The male and female students' Pre-IID-HDD mean interest rating difference was 0.35 while in their Post-IID-HDD, the mean interest rating difference was 0.00.

Research Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference between the Mean Interest Ratings of SS Students taught Herbal Drugs Discovery with GIIS and those taught with conventional method.

Table 3: Summary of Analysis of Covariance of Mean Interest Ratings of SS Students taught Herbal Drugs Discovery with GIIS and those taught with conventional method

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects	
Dependent Variable:	Post-test Interest

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	635.316 ^a	2	312.105	142.112	.000	.520
Intercept	543.503	1	543.503	260.415	.000	.051
Pre-Test Interest	35.452	1	35.452	15.460	.000	.088
Group	603.211	1	603.211	274.663	.000	.535
Error	304.955	87	2.706			
Total	100134.000	90				
Corrected Total	1013.320	89				

a. R Squared = .520 (Adjusted R Squared = .516)

Table 3 shows interest ratings of students taught herbal drugs discovery in the experimental and control groups with $F_{(1,87)} = 274.663$, $p = 0.000 < 0.005$ level of significance and η^2 partial eta squared = 0.535. The η^2 partial eta squared = 0.535 means 54% is the proportion of variance in the students' interest due to adoption of guided inquiry instructional strategy, that is, there is a significant difference between the interest ratings of students taught herbal drugs discovery using Guided Inquiry Instructional Strategy and those taught using conventional method as measured by HDDII. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Research Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference between the Mean Interest Ratings of Male and Female SS Students taught Herbal Drugs Discovery using GIIS.

Table 4: Summary of Analysis of Covariance of Mean Interest Ratings of Male and Female SS Students taught Herbal Drugs Discovery using GIIS

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects						
Dependent Variable: Post-test Interest						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	2.422 ^a	2	1.227	.560	.485	.022
Intercept	255.390	1	255.390	120.22	.000	.561
Pre-Test Interest	2.331	1	2.331	1.300	.260	.019
Gender	.000	1	.000	.000	.776	.000
Error	160.413	47	2.011			
Total	52612.000	50				
Corrected Total	154.300	49				

a. R Squared = .022 (Adjusted R Squared = .015)

Table 4 shows mean interest rating of male and female students taught herbal drugs discovery in the experimental group with $F_{(1,47)} = 0.00$, $p = 0.776 > 0.05$ level of significance with η^2 partial = 0.000. The result shows an equally higher increase in both male and female students' interest in herbal drugs discovery among the experimental group students. Hence,

the null hypothesis of no significant difference between mean interest ratings of male and female students taught herbal drugs discovery using Guided Inquiry Instructional Strategy as measured in IID-HDD is not rejected. The students' interest in herbal drugs discovery using the strategy is not based on gender.

Discussion

This study shows that the adoption of Guided Inquiry Instructional Strategy in teaching herbal drugs discovery in Chemistry enhanced students' interest during the period of the study. The improvement was statistically significant. The finding agrees with that of Ogunniyi (2022) who found that the students taught pharmacognosy using students-centered pedagogies showed significant higher interest than students taught same concept using the conventional method. Also, the findings are in consonant with those of Obioma and Anyanwu (2021) who found that the students exposed to guided discovery-based lessons demonstrated significantly higher interest than those using conventional methods.

The study also found that the use of guided inquiry instructional strategy in teaching herbal discovery in Chemistry improved both male and female students' interest. There was no significant gender difference in students' interest. The result agrees with Ugwu and Eze (2023) who found that there was no significant difference in the interest of male and female students taught Chemistry using Guided Discovery based Instruction. The findings of this study show the use GIIS is very effective in closing gender gap in students' interest. The result of this study clearly shows that Guided Inquiry Instructional Strategy (GIIS) significantly increased the interest of senior secondary students in herbal drug discovery compared to the conventional method. The post-HDDII mean interest rating of the experimental group (3.50) was notably higher than that of the control group (2.10), with a substantial mean difference of 1.40. This aligns with Rodriguez *et al.* (2020) who found in their meta-review that process-oriented guided inquiry learning (POGIL) creates better engagement and deeper understanding in science subjects compared to teacher-centered strategies.

Further supporting this, Uzezi and Zainab (2017) found that students taught volumetric analysis with a guided-inquiry approach scored significantly higher in achievement and showed greater interest than those taught with traditional methods. The present study reinforces this observation within the context of herbal drug discovery, confirming that inquiry-based models can be effectively applied to niche scientific topics relevant to local contexts, like ethnopharmacology and natural product chemistry.

Another significant finding is the absence of gender disparity in interest ratings among students taught using GIIS. Both male and female students in the experimental group recorded identical post-test mean scores (3.55), indicating that GIIS effectively promotes inclusive participation. This corroborates the work of Ugwu and Eze (2023) who reported no gender-based differences in students' interest when taught Chemistry using guided discovery. It suggests that GIIS may help bridge gender gaps in STEM subjects by providing equal engagement opportunities for all learners.

Furthermore, linking GIIS to herbal drug discovery aligns with the approach advocated by Mukherjee (2022) who emphasizes hands-on, exploratory models in validating traditional medicine. He argues that understanding herbal pharmacology requires inquiry-based engagement to help learners appreciate the complexity of plant-based therapeutics. Similarly, the integration of biological activity-guided fractionation (Chattopadhyay *et al.*, 2012) into the curriculum as a learning model would give students experiential insight into how herbal compounds are tested and developed into medicines.

Additionally, the statistically significant improvement in interest ratings (η^2 partial = 0.535) indicates a strong effect size, meaning over 50% of the variance in student interest is due to the instructional method itself. This reinforces that GIIS is not only beneficial in theory but highly impactful in practice. This resonates with the study by Fang *et al.* (2016), which demonstrated that guided inquiry promotes not only knowledge acquisition but sustained student engagement in scientific investigations.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the findings from this study contribute to the growing evidence that guided inquiry instructional strategies have transformative potential in science education, especially in emerging fields like herbal drug discovery. By enhancing interest across genders and fostering investigative skills, GIIS can bridge the gap between traditional knowledge and modern scientific inquiry, thereby enriching Chemistry education with culturally relevant and research-driven content.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

- i. Chemistry teachers should be trained in the use of guided inquiry instructional strategies (GIIS) for teaching Chemistry in secondary schools.
- ii. School administration should hold seminars for teachers to be trained in the use of other student-centered instructional strategies to improve their interest in Chemistry.
- iii. Policy makers are expected to use the information provided by this study for taking decision on the best instructional strategy like guided inquiry instructional strategy to be adopted in Nigerian Senior Secondary School Chemistry curriculum.

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